

Infrared and Raman spectra of substituted *N*-(phenyl)-2-chloroacetamides, $X_yC_6H_{5-y}NHCOCH_2Cl$ ($X = H, o/m/p$ - CH_3, Cl or NO_2 and $y = 1, 2$ or 3)

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Several substituted *N*-(phenyl)-2-chloroacetamides of the configuration $X_yC_6H_{5-y}NHCOCH_2Cl$ (where $X = H, o/m/p$ - CH_3, Cl or NO_2 and $y = 1, 2$ or 3) have been synthesized, and their infrared and Raman spectra measured in the solid state with the objective of correlating CO and NH frequencies of these substituted phenylchloroacetamides with ^{35}Cl NQR frequencies of the compounds. The study reveals that there is no systematic variation on substitution with either the infrared CO or NH absorption frequencies or the Raman scattered CO or NH frequencies. The effect of substitution in the phenyl ring in terms of either the electron-donating or electron-withdrawing groups could not be generalized. The same trend is observed even with the disubstituted phenyl-2-chloroacetamides, which may be due to the varying crystalline states of the amides on substitution, as the spectra are measured in the solid state. The infrared frequencies of the amides of the configuration $X_yC_6H_{5-y}NHCOCH_3$ (where $X = H, Cl, NO_2$ or CH_3 and $y = 1, 2$ or 3) or CH_3CONHR (where $R = H, CH_3, phenyl$ or substituted phenyl group) and $RCONH_2$ (where $R = H, CH_3, C_2H_5, (CH_3)_2, C_6H_5, (C_6H_5)_2, C_6H_5CH_2, CH_2Cl, CH_2F, CHF_2, CHCl_2, CCl_3$) have also been examined for comparison purpose. The entire data indicate that even the spectra of these compounds do not show regular trends, for the reasons stated above. The correlation of CO and NH absorption frequencies with ^{35}Cl NQR frequencies of the title compounds are also poor.

The spectroscopic and crystal structural studies give valuable informations on bond properties¹⁻⁸. Amides are of fundamental chemical interest as conjugation between nitrogen lone-pair electrons and the carbonyl π -bond results in distinct physical and chemical properties⁹⁻¹¹. The amide moiety is an important constituent of many biologically significant compounds. Therefore, an understanding of the formation, properties and reactions of amides is central to future development in such areas as polypeptides and protein chemistry. Many imides, hydroxamic acids and hydrazides exhibit pharmacological activity which has further stimulated recent interest in their chemistry. Further, many acetanilides exhibit fungicidal, herbicidal and pharmacological activities. Thus we are interested in the spectroscopic and X-ray diffraction studies of these amides in their crystalline state¹²⁻²³. We have reported ^{35}Cl NQR spectra of a number of substituted *N*-(phenyl)chloroacetamides of the configuration, $X_yC_6H_{5-y}NHCOCH_2Cl$ (where, $X = CH_3, NO_2$ or Br and $y = 1, 2$ or 3)^{12-14, 16-19}. The crystal structures of some of these *N*-phenylacetamides and chloroacetamides have also been determined^{13, 14, 20-23} to see how the $-NHCO-$ bond parameters of these compounds vary with substitution of either the electron-donating or the electron-withdrawing groups in the benzene ring and in the side-chain.

Although there are some reports on the infrared and Raman spectra of anilines and amides, there are very few reports on substituted *N*-phenylchloroacetamides^{12, 14-30}. As a part of our studies on these compounds, we have recently reported the infrared and Raman spectra of several substituted *N*-(phenyl)-2,2,2-trichloroacetamides of the configuration : $X_yC_6H_{5-y}NHCOCCl_3$ (where, $X = H, CH_3$ or NO_2 and $y = 1$ or 2)²⁹. We report herein the infrared and Raman spectra of a number of substituted *N*-(phenyl)-2-chloroacetamides of the configuration : $X_yC_6H_{5-y}NHCOCH_2Cl$ (where, $X = H, CH_3, NO_2$ or Br and $y = 1, 2$ or 3).

Results and Discussion

Infrared and Raman frequencies of substituted *N*-(phenyl)-2-chloroacetamides measured in the present investigation are shown in Tables 1-4, and those from literature^{5, 6} for the related compounds are shown in Tables 5 and 6.

Assignments of various bands in the substituted amides, in general, has been dealt in detail elsewhere^{5, 6, 24-28, 30}. Hence the general assignments of frequencies of various modes are not repeated here. But they have been broadly indicated in the Tables while listing them. Hence the discussion is limited to the effect of substitution in the phenyl ring

Table 1. Infrared frequencies (cm^{-1}) of amides of configuration, $X_yC_6H_{5-y}NHCOCH_2Cl$ with X_y

Assignment	H	2-CH ₃	3-CH ₃	4-CH ₃	2,3-(CH ₃) ₂	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	2,5-(CH ₃) ₂
NCO bend	560s	550m	560m	536s	—	558m	592m
C-Cl str	725m	723m	706s	768s	725m	710m	—
	752s	760m	798s	—	780m	722m	776m
ArCH def	860s	882m	883s	888s	—	825s	818m
	—	—	—	—	—	876m	830m
AliC-C str	905s	985s	914s	—	—	950m	—
	965s	—	962m	986s	—	975s	982m
N-Ph bend	1035m	1055m	1060m	—	—	1035m	1043m
	1198m	—	1165m	1154m	—	1162s	—
CN str	1255m	1282s	1238s	1289s	1275m	1230s	1278m
	1295m	1318m	1265m	1330s	—	1270s	1339m
	1348m	—	1326s	1385m	1375s	1335m	—
ArC=C str	1450s	1441s	1433s	1448s	1460s	1420s	1416m
NH bend	1560m	1586s	1532m	1564m	1510s	1550s	1558s
C=O str	1680s	—	—	—	1665s	1665s	1680s
	1700m	1714s	1720s	1732s	—	—	—
NH str	3280m	3340s	3365m	3365s	3290m	3238s	3268s

Assignment	2,6-(CH ₃) ₂	3,4-(CH ₃) ₂	3,5-(CH ₃) ₂	2-NO ₂	3-NO ₂	4-NO ₂	2,4,6-(CH ₃) ₂
NCO bend	612m	513s	—	575s	525s	525m	560m
	673m	690m	—	643m	606m	—	600m
C-Cl str	721m	725m	725m	773m	730s	750s	715m
	775s	775s	780m	785m	784s	775s	766m
ArCH def	—	825s	—	848s	830s	850s	848s
	—	875s	—	875m	890s	875s	—
AliC-C str	—	930m	—	920s	940m	965s	975s
	988m	970m	—	960s	992s	—	—
N-Ph bend	1035s	1135m	—	1146m	1155s	1120m	1040m
	1160m	—	—	1165m	—	1175s	—
CN str	1240m	1298s	1275m	1270m	1290m	1295s	1243s
	1392m	1340s	1375s	1380s	1350s	1340m	1335m
ArC=C str	1480m	1460s	1460s	1460s	1460s	1470s	1418s
NH bend	1550s	1557s	1540s	1555s	1555s	1570s	1540s
C=O str	1668s	1678s	1665s	1685s	1680s	1688s	1675s
NH str	3260s	3300s	3310s	3310m	3300m	3325m	3200s

Table 2. Raman frequencies (cm^{-1}) of amides of configuration, $X_yC_6H_5-yNHCOCH_2Cl$ with X_y

Assignment	H	2-CH ₃	3-CH ₃	4-CH ₃	2,3-(CH ₃) ₂	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	Assignment	2,5-(CH ₃) ₂	2,6-(CH ₃) ₂	3,4-(CH ₃) ₂	3,5-(CH ₃) ₂	2,4,6-(CH ₃) ₃
NCO bend	566m	518m	518m	571m	558m	547s	NCO bend	578m	548m	540m	559s	578s
C-Cl str	751m	714s	794m	748s	—	726s	C-Cl str	688m	705s	698s	638s	—
	774s	751s	—	798m	781m	762m		710m	759s	743s	752s	761m
ArCH def	860s	860m	819s	864s	800s	848s	ArCH def	800m	793m	825m	—	—
	—	—	—	—	—	—		815s	855s	—	—	843s
AliC-C str	1006s	971m	1000s	—	973m	974m	AliC-C str	—	982s	926m	999s	—
N-Ph bend	1151m	1158m	1170m	1178s	1094s	1124m	N-Ph bend	—	1150s	1121m	1155s	1157m
	1176s	—	1184m	1200m	1167s	1174m		—	1165s	—	1175s	1175m
CN str	1254s	1252s	1260s	1249s	1266s	1265s	CN str	1262s	1264s	1260s	1245m	1242m
	1292m	—	1332s	1292s	1329s	1334s		1326m	1325s	1322s	1382s	1332s
	1347s	1331s	—	1344s	—	1381s		—	1380s	1338s	—	—
NH bend	1561s	1552s	1542s	1551s	1587s	1542s	ArC=C str	1410m	1438m	1434s	1438m	1447m
C=O str	1677m	1662s	1673s	1670s	1662s	1655s	NH bend	1550m	1595m	1547s	1577s	1538s
	1691m	—	—	1695m	—	—	C=O str	1664m	1647s	1674s	1666s	1668s
	—	—	—	—	—	—		—	—	1692m	—	—
CH str	2951s	2968m	2968m	2955m	2915m	2925m	CH str	—	2854m	2925s	—	—
	3055m	3190	—	—	—	2956s	NH str	—	2971s	—	2977m	—

Table 3 Infrared frequencies (cm^{-1}) of amides of configuration, $X_yC_6H_{5-y}NHCOCH_2Cl$ with X_y

Assignment	H	2-Cl	3-Cl	4-Cl	2,3-Cl ₂	2,4-Cl ₂	2,5-Cl ₂	2,6-Cl ₂	3,4-Cl ₂	3,5-Cl ₂
NCO bend	560s	570s	562s	520m	537s	550s	555s	577s	–	590m
C–Cl str	725m	755s	730m	730s	726s	750m	723m	688s	690m	650m
	752s	778s	780s	776m	785s	803s	775m	740s	800s	675s
	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	778s	–	720s
ArCH def	860s	865s	878s	830s	–	820m	820m	874s	820s	–
	–	–	–	863m	–	860s	886m	–	860s	850m
AlC–C str	965s	968s	965s	965m	925s	973s	918m	926m	920m	940m
	–	–	–	–	972s	–	950m	972s	960m	–
N–Ph bend	1080m	1055s	1092s	1100m	1170m	1056s	1045m	–	1128s	1115m
	1198m	1190m	1192s	1180m	1180m	1100m	–	1100s	1150m	1180s
CN str	1255m	1380m	1268s	1280m	1282m	1280s	–	1272s	1290s	1260m
	1295m	–	1380s	1345m	1380s	1380s	1375s	1380s	1333s	1375s
	1348m	–	–	1375s	–	–	–	–	1375s	–
ArC=C str	–	1462m	1465s	1465s	1460s	1460s	1455s	1460s	1468s	1460s
NH bend	1560m	1532s	1550s	1550s	1530s	1530s	1520m	1535s	1540s	1540m
	–	–	–	–	1590s	1585s	1585s	1580m	–	–
C=O	1680s	1675s	1682s	1670s	1680s	1675s	1685s	1685s	1675s	1685s
CH str	3060m	–	2948m	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
	–	3260m	3200m	3120m	–	3250m	–	3210m	–	3200m
NH str	3280m	3285m	3275m	3270s	3280s	3355s	–	–	3320s	3330s

on the spectra of the compounds studied and their comparison and correlation with the related compounds.

N-(Phenyl)-2-chloroacetamide showed two absorption frequencies at 1680s, 1700m cm^{-1} in the infrared and two Raman scattered frequencies 1677m, 1691m cm^{-1} for the carbonyl group. This may probably indicate that there may be two molecules in the asymmetric unit of the compound in its crystalline state. We are therefore in the process of determining its crystal structure as there are no reports in

this direction. The substituted amides exhibited absorption or scattered frequencies in the region 1660–1730 cm^{-1} . These frequencies are listed in Tables 1–4. As may be seen, there is no systematic variation with the substitution. The effect of substitution in the phenyl ring in terms of electron-donating and electron-withdrawing groups could not be generalized. The same trend was observed even with the Raman scattered frequencies. The parent compound showed ν_{CO} at 1680 cm^{-1} . The other compounds with electron-donating

Table 4. Raman frequencies cm^{-1} of amides of configuration, $X_yC_6H_{5-y}NHCOCH_2Cl$ with X_y

Assignment	H	2-Cl	3-Cl	4-Cl	2,3-Cl ₂	2,5-Cl ₂	2,6-Cl ₂	3,4-Cl ₂	3,5-Cl ₂
NCO bend	566m	–	570m	523m	–	559m	513m	–	577m
	–	575s	–	–	–	601m	–	–	–
C–Cl str	751m	785m	740m	734m	790m	747s	755m	730m	–
	774s	–	785m	–	–	779s	–	–	–
ArCH def	860s	855m	889m	868m	–	–	847m	808m	801s
AlC–C str	1006s	972m	926m	–	–	–	948m	921m	941m
	–	–	974m	–	968m	–	–	–	998s
N–Ph bend	1151m	1161s	1185s	1180m	1175m	1048s	1057m	1032m	1071m
CN str	1254s	1240s	1266m	1256m	1254s	1242s	1248m	1238s	1268s
	1347s	1329m	1280s	1295m	1332s	1288s	1329m	1333s	1341m
	–	–	1331s	1345s	–	–	–	–	–
ArC=C str	1450m	–	–	–	1435m	1406m	1409m	–	1453m
NH bend	1561s	1588s	1580s	1568m	1552m	1520m	1530m	1539s	1568m
	–	–	–	–	1596s	1586s	1582s	1555s	1596s
C=O str	1691m	1675s	1680s	1712m	1620m	1683s	1681s	1675m	1690s
CH str	2951s	3080s	3069s	–	2965m	–	–	–	2968m
	3055m	–	3089m	3119m	–	–	–	–	–
NH str	–	3340s	–	–	–	3357m	–	–	3356m

Table 5. Infrared frequencies (cm^{-1}) of amides of configuration CH_3CONHR with R

Assignment	R : $\text{X}_y\text{C}_6\text{H}_{5-y}$ with X_y							
	H	CH_3	C_6H_5	4- CH_3	2-Cl	3-Cl	4-Cl	2,3- Cl_2
NCO bend	–	–	535	–	–	–	530	505
ArCH def	710	–	758	750	750	700	735	720
	–	790	–	–	–	780	–	–
	–	885	852	850	–	860	830	889
AlC–C str	–	–	963	–	–	–	956	–
N–Ph bend	–	1045	1042	–	–	–	1025	1053
	1150	1100	–	1160	–	–	1105	1165
CN str	–	–	1268	1270	–	1270	1275	1279
	–	1305	1325	–	1300	1300	1295	1308
	–	1380	–	1350	–	–	–	–
ArC=C str	1410	1415	–	–	1430	1410	–	–
	1470	–	1460	1450	1490	1470	–	1456
NH bend	–	–	1590	1590	1590	1590	1590	1578
C=O str	1670	1675	1670	1670	1700	1670	1645	–
CH str	2940	–	2860	2860	–	–	–	–
NH str	3330	3300	3230	3230	3450	3300	3260	3310
Assignment	R : $\text{X}_y\text{C}_6\text{H}_{5-y}$ with X_y							
	2,4- Cl_2	2,5- Cl_2	2,6- Cl_2	2,4,6- Cl_3	2- NO_2	3- NO_2	4- NO_2	C_2H_5
NCO bend	556	560	568	–	650	660	–	580
ArCH def	–	725	725	722	750	740	750	–
	–	–	–	816	–	810	–	–
	–	875	865	868	860	–	850	–
	889	–	–	–	–	880	–	–
AlC–C str	984	975	–	968	–	970	–	980
N–Phe bend	–	1095	1075	–	1040	1070	1010	1030
	1164	–	–	1144	1150	–	–	–
	1195	–	1195	1196	–	– 1180	1190	–
CN str	1279	1280	–	–	1280	1280	1270	–
	1303	–	1298	1294	–	–1330	1290	–
	–	1360	1377	1377	1370	–	–	1360
ArC=C str	–	–	1435	–	1430	1420	1410	1430
	–	1465	–	1464	–	1470	1490	1450
NH bend	1558	–	1530	1525	–	1540	1560	–
	–	1575	1575	–	1580	1590	–	–
C=O str	1681	1665	1680	1660	1700	1670	1670	1640
CH str	–	2960	2950	–	–	–	–	2860
	3247	–	3230	3240	–	–	–	3286
	–	3420	–	–	–	– 3330	–	–

groups in the phenyl ring showed ν_{CO} in the ranges 1637–1680 and 1700–1732 cm^{-1} . The ν_{CO} frequencies of the compounds with the electron-withdrawing groups are observed in the ranges 1670–1688 and 1700–1735 cm^{-1} .

The ν_{CO} absorption frequencies of 2-Cl and 4-Cl ring substituted compounds are lower than that of the parent compound, whereas the 3-Cl substituted compound absorbed at a little higher frequency at 1682 cm^{-1} . ^{35}Cl NQR frequency is also not observed for this compound, probably indicating that it may exist in the mixed crystalline forms and hence can not show a trend. In the case of dichloro-substituted compounds, 2,3- Cl_2 substituted compound showed same ν_{CO} frequency as that of the parent compound. The compounds with 2,4- Cl_2 and 3,4- Cl_2 substitution in the ring showed lower ν_{CO} frequencies and those with 2,5- Cl_2 , 2,6-

Cl_2 and 3,5- Cl_2 substitutions in the ring showed higher ν_{CO} frequencies than the unsubstituted compound. All mono-nitro-substituted compounds also absorbed at higher ν_{CO} frequencies than the parent compound as expected.

On methyl substitution, the ν_{CO} IR absorptions of the acetanilides shifted to lower frequencies. The same trend was observed even with the Raman scattered frequencies.

The infrared ν_{NH} frequencies of the title compounds lie in the range 3210–3430 cm^{-1} . The ν_{NH} absorption frequencies of the monomethyl substituted and 2,3-, 3,4- and 3,5-dimethyl-substituted acetanilides are higher than that of the parent acetanilide, while the ν_{NH} frequencies of the 2,4-, 2,5- and 2,6-dimethyl-substituted and 2,4,6-trimethyl-substituted acetanilides are lower than the unsubstituted compound. But the absorption frequencies of all the

monochloro-substituted and 2,4- and 2,6-dichloro-substituted acetanilides are lower than that of the parent acetanilide, while those of the 3,4-Cl₂ and 3,5-Cl₂ substituted acetanilides are higher than that of the unsubstituted compound.

Table 6. Infrared frequencies (cm⁻¹) of amides of configuration, RCONH₂ with R

Assignment	H	C ₂ H ₅	CH(CH ₃) ₂	C ₆ H ₅	(C ₆ H ₅) ₂ N	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂
NCO bend	—	—	—	685	690	—
ArCH def	—	—	780	765	760	750
	—	825	—	810	—	—
AliC-C str	—	—	1035	1030	1034	—
	1050	1080	1080	—	1080	1080
N-Ph bend	—	—	1105	1125	—	—
	—	1145	—	1145	—	—
CN str	—	1300	1285	1300	—	1300
	1395	1380	—	—	—	—
ArC=C str	—	1420	1420	1405	1425	—
	—	1475	—	1450	—	1450
NH bend	1615	—	1610	1580	1575	1590
C=O str	1700	1680	1675	1660	1660	1640
NH str	3200	3200	3210	3200	3350	3330
Assignment	CH ₂ Cl	CHCl ₂	CCl ₃	CH ₂ F	CHF ₂	CF ₃
NCO bend	650	660	650	660	640	678
ArCH def	770	770	756	—	—	—
	876	800	878	—	—	840
AliC-C str	934	—	—	1040	1072	—
N-Ph bend	1101	1140	1112	1119	1118	1130
CN str	—	1241	—	1241	—	1218
ArC=C str	1415	—	—	1436	—	—
C=O str	1680	1695	1679	—	1690	1685
NH str	3245	3250	—	—	3230	—
	3330	—	3390	3390	—	3360

The ν_{CO} and ν_{NH} frequencies of the substituted *N*-(phenyl)-2-chloroacetamides have also been compared with those of the substituted *N*-(phenyl)-2,2,2-trichloroacetamides. The ν_{CO} frequencies of the amides are generally increased on changing from ω -monochloroacetanilides to ω -trichloroacetanilides. But the ν_{NH} frequencies of these amides did not show a particular trend based on the electronic effects exerted by various groups on substitution in the benzene ring. This may be due to the varying crystalline states of the amides as the spectra were recorded in the solid state. There might have been a trend if the spectra were to be recorded in suitable solvents in dilute solutions. But the objective of the study was to correlate the infrared and Raman frequencies of the substituted *N*-(phenyl)-2-chloroacetamides in the solid state with the ³⁵Cl NQR frequencies of the compounds measured in the solid state. Hence the dilute solution spectra of the various chloroacetamides were not recorded. The trends in the variations of the Raman scattered ν_{NH} frequencies followed almost the same pattern as those of the infrared absorption frequencies.

The infrared spectra of the substituted acetamides of the configuration : $X_yC_6H_{5-y}NHCOCH_3$ (where, X = H, Cl, NO₂ or CH₃ and y = 1, 2 or 3) or CH₃CONHR (where, R = H, CH₃, phenyl or substituted phenyl group) and RCONH₂ (where, R = H, CH₃, C₂H₅, (CH₃)₂, C₆H₅, (C₆H₅)₂, C₆H₅CH₂, CH₂Cl, CH₂F, CHF₂, CHCl₂, CCl₃) are listed in Tables 5 and 6 for comparison^{5,6}. It is also evident from these data that the CO or NH infrared absorption frequencies of these compounds do not show particular trends for the reasons stated above. Hence we have undertaken a detailed study on the crystal structures of a series of the substituted *N*-(phenyl)acetamides and chloroacetamides under varying conditions of phenyl ring and side-chain substitutions. These studies are at the advanced stages and will be reported elsewhere³¹⁻³³.

Correlations of CO and NH infrared absorption and the Raman scattered frequencies and the correlation of the IR CO absorption frequencies with the ³⁵Cl NQR frequencies were also poor.

Experimental

The *N*-(substitutedphenyl)-2-chloroacetamides^{12,14,17,34} were prepared from the respective anilines and chloroacetyl chloride (Aldrich). The commercial anilines were purified either by double-distillation or by zone refining. The respective anilines in acetone or benzene were treated with chloroacetyl chloride in acetone or in benzene in the presence of excess 2 M NaOH with constant stirring. The solids separated were filtered under suction, washed thoroughly with water and dried. The amide samples were crystallized several times from ethanol. Purity of the compounds was checked by elemental analysis for C, H and N. The compounds were further characterized by determining their melting points. All other chemicals for the preparation of acetanilides were of A.R. grade.

The substituted amides prepared were *N*-(phenyl)-2-chloroacetamide, *N*-(2-methylphenyl)-2-chloroacetamide, *N*-(3-methylphenyl)-2-chloroacetamide, *N*-(4-methylphenyl)-2-chloroacetamide, *N*-(2,3-dimethylphenyl)-2-chloroacetamide, *N*-(2,4-dimethylphenyl)-2-chloroacetamide, *N*-(3,4-dimethylphenyl)-2-chloroacetamide, *N*-(3,5-dimethylphenyl)-2-chloroacetamide, *N*-(2-chlorophenyl)-2-chloroacetamide, *N*-(3-chlorophenyl)-2-chloroacetamide, *N*-(4-chlorophenyl)-2-chloroacetamide, *N*-(2,3-dichlorophenyl)-2-chloroacetamide, *N*-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)-2-chloroacetamide, *N*-(2,5-dichlorophenyl)-2-chloroacetamide, *N*-(2,6-dichlorophenyl)-2-chloroacetamide, *N*-(3,4-dichlorophenyl)-2-chloroacetamide, *N*-(3,5-dichlorophenyl)-2-chloroacetamide, *N*-(2-nitrophenyl)-2-chloroacetamide, *N*-(3-nitrophenyl)-2-chloroacetamide, *N*-(4-nitrophenyl)-2-chloroacetamide.

Infrared spectra were measured on a Nicolet Magna-550 FT-IR spectrophotometer. The resolution range was set to 1 cm^{-1} and the scanning range was from 400 to 4000 cm^{-1} . NaCl prism was used in the measurements. The spectra were recorded in the solid state (nujol). Raman spectra were measured on a Ramanor hg-25 Laser Raman spectrometer (Jobin Yvon-France). The resolution of the spectrometer was better than 0.5 cm^{-1} . The excitation source was a 4 W argon ion laser from Coherent, U.S.A. and 448 line was selected for laser Raman spectral experiments. The spectra of the anilides were recorded from their microcrystalline samples. The spectra of nitro compounds could not be taken as the compounds caught fire upon excitation by the chosen laser.

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